

The Role of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) in Shaping Digital Consumption Behavior: Implications of IT Product Adoption and User Retention

TABLE I. VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

Code	Question	Ref
Time Pressure		
TP1	I feel that the specified sales promotion time limit is generally short.	[7] [1] [10] 1
TP 2	I feel anxious when the promotional offer I purchased is about to expire.	
TP 3	I feel that the promotional offers on social media are very good.	
TP4	I am worried that the number of promotional offers will be very limited.	
Emotions		
EM1	I feel excited when using social media.	[7] [9] [6]
EM2	I feel energetic when using social media.	
EM3	I feel happy when using social media.	
EM4	I feel satisfied when using social media.	
EM5	I feel dizzy when using social media.	
EM6	I feel bored when using social media.	
EM7	Sometimes I feel annoyed when using social media.	
EM8	Sometimes I feel sleepy when using social media.	
Information Adoption		
IA1	Reviews of an item make it easier for me to make a purchasing decision.	[5] [2] [11] 1
IA2	Product reviews have increased my effectiveness in making purchasing decisions.	
IA3	A review of an item has motivated me to make a purchasing decision.	
IA4	I always consider the review ratings before trusting the information provided.	
FoMO		
FM1	I am afraid of missing out on profitable trend experiences.	[4] [6] [2]
FM2	I'm afraid that others might get the profitable trend experience without me.	
FM3	It is important to me to know about a trend that other people are going to experience.	
FM4	It's important to me to be involved in a trend that other people will experience.	
FM5	I'm afraid of not knowing what trends are going to happen to other people.	
FM6	I get anxious when I miss out on a trend that other people are going to experience.	
Extrinsic Reward		
ER1	I feel more accepted by my friends if I follow the existing trends.	[3] [1] [7]
ER2	I feel more approved by the people around me if I follow the existing trends.	
ER3	I feel more involved in social circles if I follow the existing trends.	
ER4	I feel comfortable with other people if they follow the existing trend.	
State-FoMO		
SF1	I am constantly online so as not to miss anything.	[2] [3] [9]
SF2	It is important for me to have my say on current issues on my online social networks (videos, pictures, posts, etc.).	
SF3	I am afraid of not knowing the development of trends on my social media sites.	

SF4	I constantly check my phone to keep up with any trends and news.	
Impulsive Buying		
IB1	I sometimes buy things because I like to buy, not because I need them.	[6] [2] [5]
IB2	I sometimes can't resist the urge to buy something.	
IB3	I can get very excited if I see something I want to buy.	
IB4	Sometimes I buy things when I see an interesting promotion.	
User Retention		
UR1	I will recommend trending apps to others.	[8] [3] [4]
UR2	I will continue to use trending apps in the future	
UR3	I will still choose some trending apps	
UR4	I will use trending apps over and over	
UR5	I will recommend trending apps to my close relatives	